

Is There Room for Floodplain and River Restoration? Example: Sava River Basin in Croatia

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Abstract: By regulating streams, part of the former floodplains has been converted into agricultural areas, while part of the floodplains, such as forests, natural wet meadows and marshes, have been separated from the streams due to the construction of embankments or river channel straightening. The aim of this work is to find natural and semi-natural habitats in the Sava River Basin in the Republic of Croatia that could be returned to their natural hydrological function for reducing the risk of floods and improving the hydromorphological state of the waters. The basic data used in the conducted analyses are: Flood hazard and risk maps, a digital relief model, hydromorphological monitoring data from more than 200 locations and a vector layer of water bodies defined according to the rules of the Water Framework Directive. The analyses conducted included GIS-based hydrological analyses of defining the streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km² and using the Vertical Distance to Channel Network tool for natural floodplain definition. By comparing the high probability layer of floods and the defined natural floodplain and the Map of Terrestrial Non-Forest Habitats of the Republic of Croatia (Bardi et al. 2018), areas of potential rehabilitation or restoration areas (without endangering the population and economic activities) were delineated. The analyses carried out showed that the largest compact areas that could be rehabilitated or restored, in sense of restoring river-floodplain connectivity by removing obstacle like embankment, reconnecting old meanders or flood water storage, are in the Lonja, Česma and Ilova river catchment, then parts of the river Sava floodplain from the stream Strug confluence to the river Orłjava confluence.

Keywords: river; floodplain restoration; GIS; hydromorphology.

1 Introduction

Over the past 100 years, numerous river regulation and hydrotechnical works have significantly degraded the morphology of rivers and thus the natural floodplains (Dufour and Piégay 2009, EEA 2019). In the western Europe for the past thirty years there has been active work on the restoration or rehabilitation of streams and former floodplains. While in Croatia there has recently been an initiative by state bodies and non-governmental organizations for such works.

For more than two decades, the European Union has been trying to establish the highest quality environmental management through the adoption of directives and regulations and encourage its members to restore nature, including the restoration of streams and floodplains. In the last few years, the most important documents have been

adopted, namely the European Green Deal (EC 2019) and Nature Restoration Regulation (EU 2024), which have provided additional impetus to initiate the restoration of aquatic ecosystems.

2 Materials and methods

The research area is the Sava River Basin in the Republic of Croatia (Figure 1), with a total area of approximately 25,750 km² and includes streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km². The catchment area of the streams was defined to comply with the minimum size of streams according to the Water Framework Directive (EC 2000).

Figure 1. Area of research – Sava river basin in Republic of Croatia.

Over the past 60 years, various hydrotechnical interventions have been conducted on parts of the streams in the basin to reduce the risk of flooding and large-scale land consolidation and land reclamation works to convert natural and semi-natural areas into agricultural areas. In some cases, land conversion was not completed due to drainage failure or other constraints.

The data used in the conducted analyses are: Flood hazard and risk maps (Hrvatske vode 2016), Map of terrestrial non-forest habitats of the Republic of Croatia (Bardi et al. 2018), a digital relief model resolution 25x25 m (last update years 2014-2016) (SGA 2004, 2018) and hydromorphological data (Croatian Waters 2019). Spatial analyses were performed in ArcMap and SAGA. The analyses performed included hydrological analyses of defining the direction of water accumulation, determining streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km². The initial relative relief model in relation to stream bankfull top was created by using the *Vertical Distance to Channel Network* tool (Conrad 2002).

Figure 2. Defined and active floodplain of river Sava in Croatia.

The input data were the terrain model mentioned above and the hydrographic network of streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km². This module first interpolates the stream to base elevation then, after which it subtracts the obtained values from the initial digital relief model. The flood extent was defined and the entire natural floodplain that was active before the hydrotechnical interventions was defined, considering a maximum of 2 m above the level of the stream bankfull top. The resulting floodplain was subsequently corrected using the official flood hazard map (HV 2016) (Figure 2). By intersecting the refined high flood probability layer and the lateral connection of the river with the layers of the defined natural floodplain with the Map of Terrestrial Non-Forest Habitats of the Republic of Croatia (Bardi 2018), potential areas that could be restored or rehabilitated without endangering the population and its economic activities were obtained.

Hydromorphological data collected during field research at 226 locations/sections across the study area (Figure 3) as part of the Systematic Investigation of Hydromorphological Quality Elements in Rivers from 2016 to 2019 according to the Methodology for Monitoring and Assessment of Hydromorphological Indicators (Hrvatske vode 2016).

The hydromorphological assessment is based on three groups of indicators: hydrology, longitudinal connectivity and riverbed morphology. A total of 17 indicators are defined, of which three were useful for this analysis, namely: 1. Land use (in the natural flood zone) and related characteristics on the section and water body, 2. Lateral

Figure 3. Hydromorphological score from indicators lateral connectivity and freedom of lateral movement.

connectivity of the river and the natural floodplain (length) on the entire water body, 3. Degree of lateral movement of the riverbed on the water body.

The results and findings obtained from the researched stream sections were interpolated to the upstream and downstream parts of the streams (with the same or similar morphological characteristics) using digital orthophoto (SGA 2014-2016, 2017, 2018), the cadaster of constructed water structures (Hrvatske vode 2023) and flood hazard maps (Hrvatske vode 2016), all with the aim of defining the recently active flood area.

3 Results

The length of streams with a catchment area greater than 10 km² was determined to be approximately 7,500 km. The analysis, conducted using Vertical Distance to Channel Network tool has determined that the area of the natural floodplain is approximately 7,200 km², however, this area needed to be refined to remove smaller, disconnected segments and areas from the streams that are also proven not to flood by official flood risk assessment maps (HV 2016), bringing the floodplain area to approximately 7,000 km². The area of natural and semi-natural habitats (Bardi et al. 2018) within the natural floodplain that could potentially be restored is approximately 2,250 km² (Figure 4). Also, when mapping potential areas for floodplain restoration, parts of old riverbeds were identified that could also be restored, with a total length of approximately 140 km.

Figure 4. Potential areas for floodplain and river restoration.

4 Discussion

The Vertical Distances to Channel Network tool (Conrad 2002) has proven to be in great measure suitable for floodplain delineation. The only significant errors occurred on the Sava River terrace (right terrace near the City of Zagreb) and the left terrace from the city of Nova Gradiška to the Orplava River) where small streams laterally pass over the terraces to the rivers, creating unnaturally large flooding areas, which do not occur in reality. This is an extremely large and flat area, and it is necessary to manually correct the results obtained. Data obtained from hydromorphological monitoring has shown to be dependable and suitable for defining currently active floodplains. Although the resulting area with potential for restoration is about 2,250 km², it is important to note that

these are extremely segmented areas that will be difficult to consolidate into a compact area suitable for restoration as a whole. An example is shown in Figure 5, which shows a part of the area along the streams that could simply be connected to the river and the old part of the streams restored, but also in the hinterland there is a part of the natural floodplain with natural and semi-natural habitats that is separated by agricultural areas and the reconnection with river is not likely.

Figure 5. Example of potential areas for floodplain and stream restoration.

The largest areas of floodplains that could be restored are along the rivers Ilova, Glogovnica, Lonja, Česma (see Fig. 1), then parts of the floodplain of the Sava River from the river mouth of Strug to the river mouth of Orljava and parts of Spačvanska šume.

This research also found that a large part of the streams has artificial incised riverbeds and that the embankments are not the only ones that limit the streams from natural flooding but also strengthening of the streams and reinforcement of stream banks (Čanjevac et al. 2020).

In the future, it is planned to compare the results obtained with the newly available Lidar DTM where better elevation accuracy of model is expected and to make a more detailed analysis of the potential benefits from restoration, which will include multiple parameters.

5 Conclusions

Many streams in the Sava River Basin in Croatia are regulated and limited by embankments, which therefore prevent the flooding of natural floodplains. In order to achieve the nature restoration objectives, Croatia should take certain measures by improving status of nature including streams and floodplains. The Vertical Distances to Channel Network tool appeared to be of great help for natural floodplain delineation.

This research has shown that there are large compact areas that could be restored or rehabilitated that are located near the larger rivers and parts of the floodplain of the Sava River. There are also many parts that are cut off from the river but also are far away, and it is very unlikely that they will ever be reconnected without extensive hydrotechnical works which would call into question the justification and feasibility of restorations. Artificial incision of streams could be a significant impediment in the future when re-connecting streams with floodplains.

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